

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE MODERN ECONOMY

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Abstract. *In today's developing era, innovations are increasing day by day for every field, and artificial intelligence, which is considered as a solution for almost all fields, which finds easy solutions to such problems, remains necessary for the economy, business, private entrepreneurship and public economy. This article describes the role of artificial intelligence in the modern economy, its application, the importance of the secure economy and the automated economy.*

Keywords: *Modern economy, artificial intelligence (AI), financial market, business, automation, security.*

Introduction. Artificial intelligence (AI) is algorithms or models built or designed to mimic the workings and processes of the human brain. The main purpose of these AI algorithms is to perform data analysis, prediction and management. AI is currently developing, but remains an unlikely field in many areas. If studied well, it can provide endless solutions to global problems. Its application includes defense and military, agriculture, food, medicine, energy and, of course, economy. The origin of artificial intelligence in the economy is the stage of development of the modern economy, which is revolutionizing the economy. It has the potential to transform economic research, financial markets, business operations and policy making.

Application of artificial intelligence in economy, economic forecasting. Artificial intelligence techniques such as AI and neural networks are being used to analyze large amounts of economic data and generate accurate forecasts. This includes monitoring, managing, and even predicting gross domestic product (GDP) growth, inflation, unemployment rates, stock market trends, and consumer behavior. AI models improve predictive accuracy by identifying complex data and correlations that are difficult for humans to detect. And in financial trading, AI-powered algorithms can increasingly be used in high-frequency trading, where computers analyze large data sets, execute trades, and make investment decisions autonomously. Algorithms created by artificial intelligence can quickly respond to changing market conditions, identify profitable opportunities and optimize data. Reinforcement learning techniques are also used to develop intelligent trading agents that learn and adapt through interactions with the market.

Regular automation of economic tasks. It would not be a mistake to say that automation is a convenient solution for the economy in the case of using technologies that work at a high level, reducing the human factor. It is possible to automate the small business, entrepreneurship, private and public economy by deploying algorithms in artificial intelligence, which gives us the opportunity to work with high precision. AI technologies can automate repetitive and time-consuming tasks in economic analysis, freeing economists to focus on more strategic initiatives. For example, AI can automate data collection, data cleaning, and data visualization processes. This allows economists to spend less time on high-value analysis and decision-making, leading to greater efficiency.

In the business world, it is important to know how customers behave over time, particularly in the marketing niche. For instance, each time a consumer visits a website, AI algorithms gather data, analyse it, and make predictions about the next time the customer may visit or the next website the customer is likely to visit. This is done over time and predictability in behaviour

becomes possible. This is an advantage to both the seller and the customer; the seller learns exactly what the customer desires. On the other hand, once the seller learns the customer's needs, then there will be less need for the customer to hop from one seller to the next. It saves time and related costs. Thus, AI algorithms aid in target marketing and customer engagement management.

AI can be of extreme importance in the education sector. Its learning ability can enable educationists prepare curricular that is learner-centred, after carefully observing, gathering, and analysing data on learner behaviour and interests. This ensures that learners are taught what interests them and aligns with their career goals. In addition, exam grading, and performance analysis can be done by AI, with minimal errors. Further applications are in predicting energy consumption and demand, predicting natural disasters like earthquakes, production, and operating military equipment like drones, and so on. AI robots are being used in manufacturing, agriculture, space exploration, mining and even providing emotional support and therapy. According to reports by IBM, a technology multinational, AI applications in medicine include, among others, clinical decision support and imaging analysis. Despite the upsides that come with AI, it is important to examine the downside of this approach to problem solving. There is a big possibility that once AI is globally rolled out, there will be mass unemployment of humans. Job loss will be inevitable. According to a recent survey by the World Economic Forum, estimates indicate that there will be a net loss of 14 million jobs worldwide over the next five years due to AI interventions. Goldman Sachs, a multinational investment, and financial services company, predicts that in the United States and Europe, the sectors most affected by AI will suffer job losses of up to two-thirds due to automation. However, the multinational also predicts that this automation will increase productivity and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth by 7 percent over the next ten years.

Artificial intelligence in a secure economy. AI algorithms are used to analyze financial data, identify data and make more accurate risk assessments. This is especially relevant in credit scoring, fraud detection and anti-theft. Artificial intelligence algorithms can detect anomalies and fraudulent activity, identify suspicious transactions in real time, reduce financial losses and increase security. Artificial intelligence algorithms can analyze consumer behavior and preferences to personalize marketing campaigns and optimize pricing strategies. By predicting individual preferences and data, economists can create personalized recommendations and effectively target specific customer segments. This can lead to increased customer satisfaction and higher profits. Because in artificial intelligence, the automated thinking process is generalized and can come to a definite stop in the management of emotions.

Artificial intelligence in agricultural economy. Weather affects the whole world. Artificial intelligence can be a convenient solution for accurately predicting weather changes. Low productivity is partly due to natural weather conditions. Accurate weather forecasting by trained artificial intelligence can increase farmers' productivity and income. Traffic control remains a major problem worldwide, especially in crowded and modern cities. Optimal traffic management ensures that cities are freed from congestion in the shortest possible time. This directly affects the efficiency of the supply chain and the movement of goods between producers and consumers. AI algorithms study traffic movements and make predictions on the speed of vehicles entering/exiting cities without disrupting business. Blocking cities in time has a positive impact on the environment, less time spent in traffic means less waste and pollution. Travelers also get to save on energy consumption. A study conducted by researchers at the Oak Ridge National Laboratory in Tennessee, USA, has shown that the use of artificial intelligence in traffic control can save travelers up to 25 percent in fuel consumption.

In economics and finance, there are several economic indicators, such as growth rates, interest rates, exchange rates, and inflation rates, which are critical to monetary policy management and economic stability. AI algorithms are data-driven and learn how data behaves over time, making them well-suited for forecasting these economic indicators. Accurate forecasts of these metrics are key; This can help policymakers predict the next financial crisis. In addition, for trading assets such as stocks and bonds, AI technology can predict price movements and enable trading when it is optimal to do so. An AI algorithm can be allowed to execute trades by itself even in the absence of a trader.

In short, AI can control and manage everything from economic forecasting and financial trading to risk analysis, economic automation and the production of a secure economy. This leads to the perfect management of the economy of the enterprise and even the economy of the state. As a result, we achieve a high precision economy. In general, the use of artificial intelligence in all industries can lead to better tone, lower costs and accuracy for business owners and entrepreneurs, but it can also lead to less work for ordinary workers. But control of the economy should never be completely given to AI, there should be human control over AI. There is a fear that embedding human traits and behaviour into a machine may make these machines or robots even more intelligent than we, humans, and eventually the machines will become evil and turn on us, the ones that created them, leading to our very own extinction. In short, AI could outsmart us. This is a fear that several researchers and AI executives share, including the heads of OpenAI and Google Deepmind. Whether true or not, this will be revealed over time, after more research has been done. In conclusion, considering all the advantages that AI brings, if applied in the day-to-day operations, it will enable several Governments across the globe achieve their objective of developing smart cities. However, the industry is still not well-regulated. There is a need to develop regulations that govern AI research, development, and applications. Policymakers are lagging. The application of AI could signal the start of the next industrial revolution. The progress that humanity can make with AI is impeccable. AI applications are unending, will solve several problems and unleash several opportunities in probably all sectors relevant for global development.

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